

CHEMICAL SHRINKAGE AND THERMOMECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF AN EPOXY RESIN DURING CURE BY A NOVEL IN SITU MEASUREMENT METHOD

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1 Introduction

As the composite industry grows, the use of thick parts and pieces of complex shape is increasingly in demand notably for structural applications requiring larger cross-sections to respond to mechanical stresses. The curing of thick parts remains a challenge because of their low thermal conductivity and the high heat of reaction generated during the cross-linking polymerization. This combination of low conductivity and high heat sources in the part can induce large temperature gradients and thus generate residual stresses and possible polymer degradation. The reinforcing fibers are not physically affected during processing, but the polymer matrix can shrink during cross-linking by as much as 10% [1]. These volumetric changes during processing can generate several defects such as bad surface appearance, waviness, spring-in/spring-back, dimensional inaccuracy and more, leading to a decrement of the part quality and performance [2].

The volumetric changes of thermoset resins during the curing process can be described as a combination between the thermal effect due to expansion/contraction and the chemical effect associated to shrinkage of the polymer chains [3]. In the past, several techniques have been developed for chemical shrinkage characterization [1,3]. However, most of these methods have to be coupled to a calorimeter to associate the shrinkage with the degree of cure.

In this study, a novel technique is presented, which allows simultaneous characterization of resin cure, as well as of dimensional and rheological changes that take place during polymerization. These measures are performed with an innovative thermal flux cell combined with a Dynamical Mechanical

Thermo Analyzer (DMA). Simultaneous measurements in a single device eliminate the sources of error induced while combining two or more instruments, such as the time lag or differences due to sample size.

The design of the novel DMA/flux cell enables direct injection of the liquid resin into a closed cavity. The temperature control is ensured by the thermal enclosure of the DMA. The resin is contained in a mold where the upper and lower surfaces act as heat flux sensors. Changes in temperature and thermal flux are directly monitored as well as the dynamical displacement and the stiffness during the curing process. The information obtained can then be processed in order to provide accurate data on gel time and cure kinetic behaviour. The volume and mechanical changes can also be derived from experimental data and linked to the degree of cure. Chemorheological models can then be easily created to predict the physical behaviour of the resin leading to optimization of the manufacturing of composite parts.

2 Experimental

2.1 Thermal flux cell method

The thermal, shrinkage and mechanical measurements on this work were carried out with the new thermal cell HFC200 installed on a DMA+450 from Areva-Metravib (see Figure 1). The thermal cell possesses two heat flux sensors specially conceived by Thermoflux and located on both sides of the sample. The heat flux and temperature are monitored by these flux sensors. The sample shrinkage and stiffness are respectively measured by the static displacement and dynamic response of the DMA.

2.2 Material and experimental set up

The resin system used in this work is typical Di-Glycidyl Ether of Bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy anhydride cured. Before resin injection, the temperature is stabilized in the thermal enclosure at 120°C. Resin is then injected into the sample holder. The DMA is then actioned applying a vibrating force to the sample at low displacement.

Fig.1. Novel thermo-mechanical cell HFC200.

3 Results and discussion

The heat of reaction released by the polymer during curing is determined from the measured heat flux. If the diffusion of chemical species is neglected, the reaction rate is assumed to be a unique function of the degree of conversion α and temperature T [1]:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = f(T, \alpha) \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha = \int_0^t \frac{d\alpha}{dt} \cdot dt \quad (1)$$

In the novel characterization cell described in this work, the heat of reaction was measured with the heat flux sensors in close contact with the sample. The heat of reaction was computed as the average heat flow measured at the upper and lower plates of the cell. An average heat of reaction of 337 J/g was measured for the DGEBA system tested in this study, which is very similar to the value of 321 J/g obtained with the Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC). Figure 2 illustrates the evolution of degree of cure with time using both DMA cell and DSC methods. The degree of cure evaluated with the DSC technique (full line) arises before that of the DMA. This time shift is not negligible and should therefore be compensated in the case of coupling measurements from different devices. In Figure 2, the DMA and DSC curves show a similar slope between 30 and 80% cure, however, there are

differences at the beginning and at the end of polymerization in addition to the time lag mentioned previously. Also instabilities may occur because of the temperature of the thermal enclosure.

The upper plate of the DMA cell oscillates at amplitude of 20 microns and frequency of 10 Hz. The instrument applies a controlled force to induce such oscillation to the resin sample. As the liquid resin undergoes polymerization, the dynamic force required to apply a constant amplitude oscillation will increase from gelification to full cure. Then, knowing the variation on dynamic force, the change in mechanical properties of the resin can be followed during polymerization. On the other hand, when the resin shrinks during cure, the instrument adjusts the position of the upper plate so that it is in continuous contact with the sample. Measuring the static position of the upper plate is then a direct evaluation of the volume changes occurred during resin polymerization.

Fig.2. Comparison between degree of cure measure with DSC and DMA cell.

As shown in Figure 3, at the early beginning of the test, when the resin is fully liquid, a stiffness of 10 N/m is measured by the DMA-flux cell. This small stiffness is due to the moving liquid under dynamic compaction. The stiffness increases linearly the first 200 seconds up to 50 N/m corresponding to 20% of cure. At this stage the polymer chains start to form an inter-connected tridimensional network resulting in a quick increment of mechanical properties shown by sudden change to a steeper slope in stiffness. The $\tan \delta$ is the ratio between the stored and loss factors of the dynamic stiffness. The $\tan \delta$ in Figure 3 shows a peak at 230 seconds representing a maximum of the dissipating energy of the sample. This peak is associated to the gelification of the

polymer resin (i.e. first apparition of the infinite polymer network) and corresponds to a stiffness of 100 N/m in Figure 3. After this point, the elastic storage modulus increases and Tan δ decreases. The increment of sample stiffness shows then a similar behavior than the degree of cure. A maximum stiffness of 10^7 N/m was obtained for the fully cured resin after 1000 seconds.

Fig. 3. Evolution of stiffness and Tan δ with time during isothermal polymerization at 120°C.

Figure 4 illustrates the evolution of stiffness during polymerization for a sample tested at 10 Hz and 20 microns oscillation amplitude. This evolution was found to be nonlinear from 33% of cure which corresponds to the gelification point. The nonlinear relation between stiffness and degree of cure was reported by previous studies of Ruiz et al. [1, 5] for polyester resins and more recently Abou Msallem et al. [6] for epoxy resins. These approaches take into account the transition from viscoelastic to elastic behaviour and the glass transition temperature as well.

As mentioned previously, at gelification, the sample stiffness arises rapidly due to the formation of the 3-dimensional network. This state of polymerization is then defined as the gel point. For the case study, this reference value cure α_{gel} corresponds to a gelification at 33% of cure as illustrated in Figure 4. The evolution of the stiffness suggests a logarithmic relation with the degree of cure as follows:

$$\frac{\log K}{\log \alpha} = B \quad \text{and} \quad \log K = B \left[\frac{(1 - \alpha_{gel}) \log \alpha + 1}{(1 - \alpha_{gel})} \right] \quad (2)$$

where K is the stiffness, α the degree of cure and B and α_{gel} are constants determined from the experimental results. Their values for the epoxy-anhydride resin studied are reported in Table 1.

Fig. 4. Stiffness as function of degree of cure for different parameters configuration and proposed model. Isothermal polymerization at 120°C.

Table 1. Parameters of proposed models to predict stiffness and resin shrinkage

Stiffness model	Shrinkage model
Equation (2)	Equation (6)
B	C
11.225	5.050
α_{gel}	α_c
0.332	0.535

The linear shrinkage $l(t)$ was defined as the difference in the position $x(t)$ of the upper sample holder from its reference value x_{ref} as follows:

$$l(t) = \frac{x(t) - x_{ref}}{t_i} \quad (3)$$

where t_i is the initial thickness of the resin sample. Previous experimental studies have been conducted relating the volumetric changes that occur during thermosets processing. Hill et al. [3] proposed that the overall volumetric changes of a thermoset resin during cure can be considered as a combination between thermal expansion/contraction and polymerization shrinkage as follows:

$$\left(\frac{1}{V_0} \frac{dV}{dt} \right)_{Overall} = \left(\frac{1}{V_0} \frac{dV}{dt} \right)_{Thermal \ contribution} - \left(\frac{1}{V_0} \frac{dV}{dt} \right)_{Polymerization \ shrinkage} \quad (4)$$

The first term on the right-hand represents the bulk thermal expansion/ contraction contribution whereas

the second term the shrinkage associated to the chemical curing reaction. This latter was expressed proportional to the reaction rate as follows:

$$\left(\frac{1}{V_0} \frac{dV}{dt} \right)_{\substack{\text{Polymerization} \\ \text{shrinkage}}} = C \frac{d\alpha}{dt} \quad (5)$$

where C is a constant determined from the experimental results. In this work, chemical shrinkage was measured by the static displacement of the upper plate of the DMA cell during resin cure.

As illustrated in Figure 5, shrinkage is noticeable from 280 seconds and follows a tendency similar to the degree of cure (see Figure 2), with a maximum shrinkage of 3% after 1000 seconds. Figure 6 shows the evolution of the chemical shrinkage of the resin as a function of degree of cure. Shrinkage is measured after the gelification of the resin at 54% of cure. From this point, a linear dependence of the degree of cure is observed up to 95% of cure. However, a divergence appears at the very end of cure. This divergence was not studied in the present work and will be the aim of future researches. At the end of cure, the reaction is controlled by the diffusion of chemical species; this may contribute to the deviation of the linear shrinkage trend. This behaviour is consistent with previous researches on thermoset resins [1, 3, 7] and can be modelled by the following equation:

$$l = C(\alpha - \alpha_c) \quad (6)$$

where l is the linear shrinkage, α the degree of cure and C and α_c are constants determined from the experimental results and presented in Table 1 for the epoxy-anhydride resin studied. The maximum measured shrinkage was of 3.2 % which is in the usual range of epoxies [8].

4 Conclusion

This article presents a novel characterization technique for the measurement of thermal, chemical and mechanical properties of thermosets during polymerization. The instrument developed in this work is based on a DMA equipment and implement heat flux sensors to follow resin cure. It has the advantage of measuring several properties of the polymer in-situ, resulting in a better understanding

of the complex phenomena that take place during curing. It also has the advantage of speeding the characterization process avoiding tedious analyses in several instruments such as DSC, DMA and TMA and reducing the source of error due to time lag or sample size. This novel instrument opens a new window for process optimization. Industries in the aerospace, automotive, sports and industrial field will benefit from this new scientific approach.

Fig.5. Resin shrinkage with time during isothermal polymerization at 120°C.

Fig.6. Resin shrinkage as function of degree of cure and proposed model during isothermal cure at 120°C.

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